

Short communication

SECOND RECORD OF THE ASIAN SPECIES *SCOLYTOPLATYPUS TYCON* BLANDFORD, 1893 (CURCULIONIDAE: SCOLYTINAE) FOR THE NORTH CAUCASUS

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Species of the genus *Scolytoplatypus* C. F. C. Schaufuss, 1891 are distributed in the Afrotropical and Oriental regions. However, cases of species invasion into other areas are common. After fourteen years on the territory of North Caucasus (Russia: Republic of Adygea), one far-eastern species, *Scolytoplatypus tycon* Blandford, 1893 (Curculionidae: Scolytinae), was recorded for a second time.

Species of the genus *Scolytoplatypus* C. F. C. Schaufuss, 1891 (over 50 species worldwide) are distributed in the Afrotropical and Oriental regions, with a few in the temperate areas of Japan to India (Bright & Skidmore, 2002; Beaver & Liu, 2007; Maiti & Saha, 2009; Jordal, 2018; Liao *et al.*, 2022). Twenty-six species of *Scolytoplatypus* (Curculionidae: Scolytinae) are reported in the Palearctic region, and three are known from the Russian Far East: *Scolytoplatypus daimio* Blandford, 1893, *S. mikado* Blandford, 1893 and *S. tycon* Blandford, 1893 (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2023). All known species of *Scolytoplatypus* are ambrosia beetles (Beaver & Gebhardt, 2006), which cultivate fungi as the only food source for larvae and adults (Liao *et al.*, 2022).

The Palearctic range of *Scolytoplatypus tycon* includes China (Heilongjiang), Taiwan, North and South Korea, Japan, and the south of the Russian Far East (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2023). From Russia, this species was recorded in Khabarovsk and Primorsky krai and Amur and Sakhalin (Sakhalin and Kunashir islands) areas (Krivolutskaya, 1996). The only record of *S. tycon* in Europe is in the North Caucasus (Republic of Adygea, "Lesnaya skazka", 44°21'00"N 40°11'23" E), where the beetle was collected in 2009 (14.04 – 01.05) in a trap with fermenting beer and honey (Zamotajlov & Nikitsky, 2010). Other records (except for the northwestern Caucasus) of this species in Europe or North America are currently unknown.

As a result of short-term expeditionary research in May 2023 in the Maykop district of the Republic of Adygea, new records of this species, alien to Europe, were made (Mandelshtam, 2019).

Figure 1. *Scolytoplatypus tycon* (male) from the Republic of Adygea (2023). Scale bar – 1 mm

***Scolytoplatypus tycon* Blandford, 1893 (Fig. 1)**

Material examined

Russia: Republic of Adygea, Maykop district, “Gornaya legenda”, 44°15'13.5"N 40°12'03.1"E, light trap, 20.05.2023; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀; leg. A. S. Sazhnev.

New (second) records were made 11 km south of the previous ones (Zamotajlov & Nikitsky, 2010). Even though it is a broad polyphagous species (Stark, 1952; Wood & Bright, 1992; Krivolutskaya, 1996), *Scolytoplatypus tycon* probably has not spread widely in the North Caucasus for 14 years (2009-2023) because its larvae feed on the ambrosial fungus and the beetles are monogamous (Liao *et al.*, 2022), not prone to inbreeding and incapable of parthenogenesis (Mandelstam, 2019).

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ДРУГИ НАПАД АЗИЈСКЕ ВРСТЕ *SCOLYTOPLATYPUS TYCON*
BLANDFORD, 1893 (CURCULIONIDAE: SCOLYTINAE) ЗА ПОДРУЧЈЕ
СЕВЕРНОГ КАВКАЗА

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ИЗВОД

Врсте рода *Scolytoplatypus* C. F. C. Schaufuss, 1891 су распрострањене у афротропским и оријенталним областима. Међутим, чести су случајеви инвазије у друга подручја. После четрнаест година на територији Северног Кавказа (Русија: Република Адигеја), по други пут је забележена једна далекоисточна врста, *Scolytoplatypus tycon* Blandford, 1893 (Curculionidae: Scolytinae).

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